

concept

D5.1- First plan for dissemination
and exploitation of results (PDER)

30/06/2024

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe programme under the Grant Agreement 101135946. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

D5.1 FIRST PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS (PDER)

Work package	WP 5
Due date	30/06/2024
Submission date	28/06/2024
Deliverable lead	F6S
Version	0.4
Authors	Cristiana Peres and Filipa Sousa (F6S)
Reviewers	Henrik Sønsteby (UIO)
Abstract	This document shares the strategy for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plans for the CONCEPT project.

DOCUMENT DISSEMINATION LEVEL

Dissemination Level

X	PU - Public
	SEN - Sensitive

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
0.1	06.05.2024	Structure and first inputs	F6S
0.2	21.05.2024	Communication and dissemination strategy	F6S
0.3	10.06.2024	Exploitation plan (first)	F6S
0.4	21.06.2024	Final revision	F6S

DISCLAIMER

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe programme under the Grant Agreement 101135946. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

Grant Agreement No.: 101135946

Call: HORIZON-CL4-2023-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-CNECT

Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2023-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-11

Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

PARTNERS

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	8
2	COMMUNICATION STRATEGY	9
2.1	VISUAL IDENTITY	10
2.1.1	LOGO	10
2.1.2	COLOURS AND TYPOGRAPHY	11
2.2	TARGET AUDIENCES AND KEY MESSAGES.....	11
2.3	PHASES OF ENGAGEMENT	12
2.4	CONTENT CREATION	14
2.5	COMMUNICATION CHANNELS.....	15
2.5.1	LINKEDIN	15
2.5.2	WEBSITE	16
3	DISSEMINATION STRATEGY	16
3.1	MAIN CHANNELS.....	17
4	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS	18
5	EXPLOITATION	20
5.1	METHODOLOGY	20
5.1.1	EXPLOITATION METHODOLOGY PHASES.....	22
5.1.1.1	PHASE 1 - IDENTIFY.....	24
5.1.1.2	PHASE 2 - CHARACTERISE.....	26
5.1.1.3	PHASE 3 - OWN.....	28
5.1.1.4	PHASE 4 - EXPLOIT.....	29
6	CONCLUSIONS.....	30
7	ANNEXES.....	32

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1- CONCEPT LOGO 10

FIGURE 2-CONCEPT COLOURS 11

FIGURE 3- TYPOGRAPHY..... 11

FIGURE 4- CONCEPT EXPLOITATION METHODOLOGY PHASES.....23

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1- PHASES OF ENGAGEMENT	12
TABLE 2-CONTENT	14
TABLE 3- KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS	18
TABLE 4- PHASE 1: IDENTIFICATION ACTIVITIES	26

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable D5.1 introduces the CONCEPT Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan. It is a comprehensive living document outlining the tools, channels, and activities to be implemented throughout the project to maximise its impact and results. It defines the strategy, activities, tools with which the project communicates with its stakeholders and the timing of the various activities throughout its lifetime.

A structured communication strategy guides the content created by the project, aligning it with the objectives and helping the messages to be transmitted in a clear and captivating way. The project defined four target audiences: European ECS/ICT R&I entities, European ECS/ICT industry, Users of European ECS/Industry, general audience.

CONCEPT has four different phases of engagement: (1) building, (2) piloting, (3) using, and (4) stabilisation, occurring during the project lifetime. The first three specifically emphasising using results of the project. Dissemination activities will continue after the end of the project to guarantee the sustainability of results and the impact within the fourth phase.

The project created a visible brand associated with a strong impact, contributing to building a trustworthy project and increasing awareness within the target communities. The dissemination strategy is based on industry domain events, workshops, journal papers, business and industry magazine articles, white papers, and other scientific publications.

This document presents the communication channels established for the project: website and social media channels (LinkedIn), and planned content categories associated with target audiences and channels.

This document outlines the project's exploitation roadmap, the methodology used for exploitation, and the anticipated preliminary results. It lays out the strategy to develop a comprehensive exploitation plan that will be executed throughout the CONCEPT project's lifecycle and beyond.

1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable establishes a communication and dissemination strategy that will be followed by all consortium partners throughout the programme, ensuring that all communication efforts follow the defined guidelines and have the expected results.

The core objective of CONCEPT is to contribute to the development of created to change and develop alternatives to traditional silicon semiconductor technology. By harnessing the expertise of leading European partners in chemistry, materials science, and device engineering, we're working to create a different, sustainable approach to help the demand for powerful and energy-efficient devices. CONCEPT will use atomic layer deposition (ALD) – enabling the integration of epitaxial functional complex oxides in neuromorphic and photonic devices at low temperatures. The communication strategy presented not only focuses on promoting the project itself but also focuses on promoting those working on the project.

This document also defines the project's exploitation roadmap and the exploitation methodology employed. It represents the strategy to obtain a definitive exploitation plan that will be implemented throughout the CONCEPT project life cycle and beyond.

The exploitation plan presented here represents the first version, which will be updated to the second version in month 24 (D 5.2, M24 - Revised plan for dissemination and exploitation of results (PDER)), leading to the third and final version in month 40 (D 5.4, M40 - Final Plan).

2 COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

A structured communication strategy guides the content created by the project, aligning it with the objectives and helping the messages to be transmitted in a clear and captivating way. The first step in every communication strategy is to define objectives that will guide the activities and achieve the goals proposed for the project.

We chose two main objectives, which are always at the forefront of our minds when we carry out our actions and develop our communication materials.

Short term goal – a primary goal that suits the first phases of the project: building and piloting.

- To generate awareness for the need of developing alternatives to traditional silicon semiconductor technology.

Long term goal – an objective that accompanies all phases of the project and after the project including the dissemination of results.

- To share the relevant developments and outcomes in the project, including the n atomic layer deposition reactor enabling complex oxide epitaxy on wafer-scale (8") for proof-of-concept on the impact towards ICT industry.

The goal of our visual identity is to make the project memorable and easily recognisable. We also aimed for a clean, minimalist, easy-to-understand identity. The project addresses complex topics that are challenging for the general public to understand. We aimed to present the information on our public channels in a very clear and accessible manner.

The next steps of a communication strategy are to define target audiences, communication channels and type of content. In the next paragraphs, we will explain in more detail the following topics:

- Visual Identity
- Target audiences
- Phases of engagement
- Content creation
- Communication channels

The project's communication strategy is under continuous development and will be reviewed and updated at key moments of the project.

2.1 VISUAL IDENTITY

The visual identity aims to be strong, easy recognisable and coherent throughout the project. Maintaining a consistent visual language, we ensure that all project materials are immediately identifiable and align with our overall brand image. This coherence is crucial for establishing a unified presence across various platforms and channels, enhancing the project's memorability and impact. Our design elements, including logos, colors, typography, and graphics, are carefully curated to reinforce this identity.

2.1.1 LOGO

The CONCEPT logo aims to convey the idea of transformation to the viewer. By integrating round elements that symbolize the atom and incorporating the 'C' from the project's name, the logo represents the progress inherent in our project.

FIGURE 1- CONCEPT LOGO

2.1.2 COLOURS AND TIPOGRAPHY

The colours were chosen to match the project’s identity and set the tone for all visuals created for the project, whether in the form of official documents (deliverable and presentation templates) or promotion materials (including visuals for social media and offline materials). These colours are associated with the electromagnetic radiation: purples, blue-ish, orange.

Two types of fonts were chosen and used in visuals and templates to maintain the coherence of all materials. The sans serif font a AFACAD is used for titles and some subtitles. A secondary font, AVENIR, was selected to be used at different levels; to ensure that information presented as longer textual passages is published in simple and easy to read.

FIGURE 2-CONCEPT COLOURS

FIGURE 3- TYPOGRAPHY

2.2 TARGET AUDIENCES AND KEY MESSAGES

Having a clear understanding of who we want to reach is essential to developing strategic target messages and ensuring appropriate communication of the project and its results. CONCEPT targets audiences and respective key messages are:

- **European ECS/ICT R&I entities (RTO's, universities, accelerators):** The CONCEPT platform allows integration of epitaxial complex oxides by ALD, without sacrificing on film quality. This solves existing challenges in Information and communications technology (ICT) field but also opens new doors for exotic new technology. The CONCEPT platform is open for all.
- **European ECS/ICT industry:** CONCEPT opens for integration of functional complex oxides at industrially friendly conditions; low temperatures, large areas, ALD-ecosystem already in place.
- **Users of European ECS/Industry:** New devices based on the CONCEPT platform will kick off a new paradigm in the production of ICT in Europe. Significant possibilities for entrepreneurship in new devices are expected.
- **General audience:** CONCEPT will bring new technology with significant positive impact on the public.

2.3 PHASES OF ENGAGEMENT

CONCEPT has four different phases of engagement (see Table 1): **(1) building**, **(2) piloting**, **(3) using**, and **(4) stabilisation**. Dissemination activities will continue after the end of the project to guarantee the sustainability of results and the impact within the fourth phase.

TABLE 1- PHASES OF ENGAGEMENT

Phases	Objectives	Target groups
1- Building (M1-M12)	Ensures proper awareness raising and initial engagement of the relevant stakeholders; helps creating a strong network in the business communities to prepare the EU industry transition journey and; establishes synergies with other running projects, initiatives, business networks and associations as well as specific platforms and EU agencies with the aim of involving them	All relevant stakeholders.

	during project implementation.	
2- Piloting (M6-M18)	First results are expected already at a very early stage of the project such as the participation of industry players in the challenges definition, in parallel with tech-savvy innovators engagement in early-stage activities.	European industry players, industry associations, digital innovation hubs (DIH), enterprise Europe networks (EEN), industry and business experts, accelerators, incubators, universities/research technology organization (RTO), private and public business support organizations, relevant public authorities.
3- Using (M12-M42)	Phase in dissemination already puts a specific focus on actual use of the results within and outside the group of organizations already reached. The main aim is the uptake of the results; support evidence-based decision-making; encourage tech-savvy innovators and partners to go beyond the experiment in their transition journey with the available tools; encourage other EU entities/ industries beyond the project; sign collaboration/ investment agreements for after the end of the project actions.	Innovators and industry decision-makers, European associations, DIHs, EENs, industry and business experts, private and public business support organizations, social innovation training providers, relevant public authorities, <i>etc.</i>
4- Stabilisation (M36-M48)	Depending on the outcome of the exploitation planning the assets will be prepared for transfer to either one party in charge of exploitation and valorization of the assets with sustainable potential or to various parties. Agreements and action plans will be developed that will define the conditions under which these assets will be further disseminated and exploited.	All relevant stakeholders.

2.4 CONTENT CREATION

The content produced by CONCEPT will be repurposed and adapted from the website to social media, and vice versa for further dissemination and reach.

Table 2-Content has a detailed breakdown of the associated categories, content, audiences, and channels.

TABLE 2-CONTENT

Category	Content	Channel
Infographics	Programme milestones	Social media Website.
Media Press Visibility Presence at conferences	Programme milestones (number of companies reached, successful cases); Events	Social media Website.
Videos	Research and technological developments;	Social media Website.
Interviews	Consortium partners: Who are they? What do they do? What do they think about the project?	Social media Website; Media Publications.
Articles	Explanation of the CONCEPT project Scientific papers.	Social media Media Publications.
	Trends; Relevant reports; EU news; Industry news.	Social media Website; Media Publications

2.5 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Having a strong online presence is crucial for getting our project's message out there. CONCEPT uses the website and LinkedIn channel to promote activities and output of the project regularly. These platforms connect us with our stakeholders, and we think of them as the front window to our project. So, it's vital that we make them relevant, with engaging and congruent content.

- **Engaging:** our content shouldn't be just plain information. We work to have content that is interesting. We want to keep our stakeholders in the loop and remind them why and what are we working on.
- **Consistent:** No matter where someone encounters our project (LinkedIn or website), our style, tone, and look should be consistent across.

Through our website and social media, we're not only sharing the project story but also engaging with our stakeholders and making sure our project's objectives, mission and opportunities are heard loud and clear.

2.5.1 LINKEDIN

CONCEPT created a [LinkedIn company](#) page because of the project consortium's strong presence with connections to highly relevant actors for the programme. Content is distributed through partner company profiles and reshared from personal accounts. LinkedIn is sustained by content created by the project, but also by external parties - resharing relevant content.

- **Frequency of posts:** two to three times per week throughout the project, increasing in frequency during events for example.
- **Type of content published**
 - **Information on project activities:** objectives, events, results.
 - **Consortium partners:** information on our partners, quotes, interviews, relevant opportunities and work.
 - **Articles:** created by the project partners and from external parties related to the scope of the project.

- **Synergies:** sharing other project partners' information and opportunities
- **Industry news:** sharing relevant insights about the field.

2.5.2 WEBSITE

The CONCEPT website has its main domain at <http://www.conceptproject.eu/>. The website is the most complete source of information for interested parties being the main information channel. It serves as a contact point for relevant stakeholders, informing them clearly and effectively of all aspects of the project, such as up-to-date activities, events, and information about the consortium members. The website is a repository for scientific publications and deliverables.

2.5.2.1 STRUCTURE

The website currently has the following structure:

- Homepage – main information about the project with hyperlinks for crucial areas
- About – information about the objective and scope
- Our methodology – development of the work
- Who are we? – presentation of partners
- Resources – scientific publications and deliverables
- Insights – articles

3 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The purpose of dissemination activities is to transfer knowledge and results to enable others (scientific community, industry, or policymakers) to use and take up results, maximising the impact of the research done by the project.

CONCEPT will use the background of its partners (as part of universities and industry experts) and their proactive participation in conferences and events related to the industry to ensure

interaction with the target audiences' scientific community and industry, to achieve a long-term impact and market uptake of the project outcomes.

To ensure that our information, results, and objectives are well received, we will develop materials, such as leaflets, videos, or specific event materials, to help the dissemination of results, to support our content, and to further disseminate the project brand. The dissemination strategy is planned to start in phase two of the project Piloting (M6-M18) and will continue to the next phases.

3.1 MAIN CHANNELS

To engage and interact with the above target audiences and, as mentioned before, CONCEPT will take advantage of:

- a) Industry domain events
- b) Workshops and webinars
- c) Journal papers, business, and industry magazine articles
- d) White papers/scientific publications

a) Industry domain events

Participation in events will raise awareness of the project activities and disseminate the project outputs, presenting objectives and results. These participations help us to establish a link with the target stakeholders and involve them in future activities. An event calendar was created to list the relevant events and keep partners updated. Partners are encouraged to contribute to this event mapping calendar by adding relevant events.

b) Workshops and webinars

To share the results and impacts, the project aims to organise at least one workshop involving different stakeholders and other projects funded under the same call.

c) Scientific publications

Taking advantage of our project partners' academic backgrounds, we will produce scientific publications to disseminate our results and contribute to third-party learning. These publications are one of the most important dissemination channels for sharing results with relevant stakeholders, creating knowledge impact, and enabling audiences to explore the achieved results further.

d) Other articles

The partners will take advantage of their role and expertise to provide relevant content about as an outcome of the project, adding value to the sector. These articles can be published in relevant businesses magazines or newspapers in an online or offline format.

4 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

CONCEPTS tracks and analyses several key performance indicators (KPIs) to ensure its communication and promotion activities are effective, and the strategy is optimised accordingly.

TABLE 3-KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

General	CONCEPT community	10
	Event participation (no. events)	10
	Event participation (no. attendees to CONCEPT presentations)	1000
	Project website/dashboard	5000
	Social media	500
	Synergies with existing networks (collaboration agreements)	3
	Media/press visibility	4
Specific/ Shared with partners	No. of workshops organized	3
	Number of multi-stakeholders events	1
	N° of attended events	3

N° of events with project's presentation	5
N° of conference papers	15
N° of journal papers	8
N° of articles in industry magazines	5
N° of industry contact points	40
N° of industry communities informed about the project	10
N° of projects with synergies	5
N° of joint activities	3
N° of internal partners' events	10
N° of training webinars	3
N° of working groups	3
Number of projects presentations in standardisation meetings	2
N° of unique visitors	1000
N° of page views	3000
N° of followers (twitter & linkedin together)	2000
N° of engagements	1000
N° of posts	20
N° of interactions	1000
N° of press releases	6
N° of project factsheets, brochures and banners	3
N° of newsletters	8
N° of project newsletter subscribers	250
N° of videos	2
N° of views per video	2500

	N° of blog posts in relevant channels	10
--	---------------------------------------	----

5 EXPLOITATION

This document is a strategic guide for CONCEPT's exploitation activities throughout the project's lifetime. Based on a tailored innovation management methodology, its primary goal is to facilitate the development of a cohesive exploitation strategy for CONCEPT's results post-project completion. Through the activities conducted within the project, partners will gain a clear understanding of the exploitation pathway for CONCEPT's results and the steps needed to advance in any of the three selected exploitation routes: research, technological, and commercial.

This document should be treated as a strategic roadmap, essential for consortium members to comprehend the exploitation process. It provides a step-by-step guide on the envisioned exploitation activities within the project duration and outlines the specific contributions expected from each partner. This ensures the development of tailored individual and collective exploitation plans that align with their unique business needs and CONCEPT's project objectives.

The ultimate goal of the exploitation activities outlined in this document is to disseminate the CONCEPT project's results to a broader audience and support the exploitation partners in advancing the technologies developed within the project.

5.1 METHODOLOGY

Optoelectronic and neuromorphic devices that use ferroelectrics are well-known in principle. Small-scale prototype devices have demonstrated functionality in relevant environments, suggesting that for some applications, the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is at a mid-development stage and should progress towards deployment. However, advancing to higher TRLs is challenging due to the laboratory techniques currently used to construct these devices. New development is necessary for the technology to transition into the deployment phase.

Functional complex oxide deposition by Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD) is one of the enabling technologies that may facilitate this transition. One of the significant impacts of the CONCEPT project is to support the transition of these new ICT technologies into late development and early deployment stages.

Low-temperature ALD of functional complex oxides is a technology that has recently emerged from its nascent stage. A significant breakthrough was achieved with the deposition of Lanthanum Nickel Oxide (LNO) in 2020, followed by the deposition of other functional materials. This technology is on the cusp of moving from the research phase to development TRLs.

CONCEPT aims to advance the ALD epitaxy of complex oxides from late research TRLs (approximately 2-3) to development TRLs (approximately 3-4). This advancement will, in turn, enable novel ferroelectric ICT technologies to progress to later development TRLs (4-5). CONCEPT aims to facilitate this progression by developing ALD technology towards medium TRLs and enhancing the fundamental understanding of ferroelectrics at the nanoscale.

The development and implementation of a unified exploitation strategy will allow the streamline of these advances and require the effective participation of each partner.

An exploitation strategy must adopt a lean approach to be effective and actionable. This involves two key aspects: first, fostering continuous feedback from users to solution developers as early as possible, and second, ensuring that solution providers continuously assess the product's feasibility and long-term viability.

CONCEPT will use a customised methodology based on the principles of the Customer Discovery Loop to create a robust exploitation plan that the relevant project partners will adopt.

The execution of this methodology involves a two-fold inward and outward process. Internally, significant effort will be directed toward understanding solution developers' and exploitation partners' perceptions and willingness to exploit and commercialise the solutions (when possible, depending on the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of each specific key exploitable result (KER)). This ensures the viability of the exploitation scenarios from the partners' point of view. Externally, the focus is on engaging early adopters and end-users outside the project to enhance uptake beyond the CONCEPT project. This will involve testing the project's results by validating their:

- **Desirability:** Addressing customer-related uncertainties.
- **Feasibility:** Testing available technology, resources, activities, and partners.
- **Viability:** Conducting financial opportunity assessments.

This focus on end-user needs will ensure that the final products are well-adapted to the market, thereby increasing the chances of successful technology adoption. The outcome of this methodology is the achievement of a validated business model that allows partners to position themselves with a clear go-to-market plan. The exploitation process will progress from hypothesising potential market needs to actual market introduction to increasing customer readiness levels throughout the project, wherein customers are involved in extensive product testing.

In the context of European-funded research projects, creating an effective exploitation plan is crucial for maximising the impact of the developed technologies. This involves aligning the project's goals with market needs and ensuring compliance with funding requirements, intellectual property management, and collaboration with stakeholders across various sectors. By integrating these elements into the exploitation strategy, CONCEPT aims to deliver innovative solutions that are both market-ready and capable of generating significant economic and societal benefits.

5.1.1 EXPLOITATION METHODOLOGY: PHASES

CONCEPT is producing a set of results, which the consortium will exploit in different ways. This plan establishes the phases and activities that will be implemented throughout the project to develop relevant exploitation strategies. The overall exploitation plan for the project has four different phases, as presented in Figure 4.

FIGURE 4-CONCEPT EXPLOITATION METHODOLOGY PHASES

This process is dynamic, and work in one phase may lead to refinements in earlier phases and outputs. Each phase includes activities designed to produce specific outputs, ultimately contributing to a robust exploitation plan for the project's results. These outputs support the project's reporting activities and make the results available on the funding and tenders portal.

As the exploitation manager, F6S facilitates this process. F6S has outlined the activities for each phase and prepared templates for the corresponding outputs (templates included in Annexes). To ensure comprehensive input and validation, F6S will facilitate workshops during each phase to increase the partners' engagement with the process. The partners responsible for developing each result are considered its owners and are tasked with elaborating its exploitation plan.

The following sections describe each phase's activities, processes, and outputs, identifying the involved partners and their roles. The exploitation strategy will be re-evaluated before month 24 to assess its effectiveness and make any necessary adjustments so that these can be included in the second version of this document (D 5.2). Around this time, partners will also decide on pursuing the support of the horizon results booster to further develop some of the project's key exploitable results.

5.1.1.1 PHASE 1 - IDENTIFY

The Grant Agreement (GA) already identifies the project's results; however, reviewing them and evaluating their potential and target audiences is crucial. The objective of this phase is to provide a detailed overview of all results, categorised by type, and to select those with the highest potential for exploitation, known as the key exploitable results (KER).

The output of this phase will be a comprehensive table of results containing the following information:

- **Result Name**
- **Short Description**
- **Result Type**
 - **SCI** — Scientific discovery, model, theory
 - **PROD** — Product (new or improved)
 - **SERV** — Service (new or improved)
 - **PROC** — Industrial process (new or improved)
 - **BUS** — Business model (new or improved)
 - **DSG** — Design (new or improved)
 - **METH** — Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)
 - **PO** — Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy
 - **EVNT** — Event (conference, seminar, workshop)
 - **STAFF** — Qualified personnel exchanges

- **LEARN** — Learning and training (modules, curricula)
- **INFRA** — New or improved infrastructures or facilities
- **Owners**
- **Key Results (KER)**
 - High scientific potential
 - High societal potential (other than climate or environmental)
 - High societal potential
 - High technological, business, or economic potential
 - High policy or regulatory potential
 - N/A
- **Target Audience**
 - Researchers
 - Industry and business partners
 - Investors
 - EU Institutions and agencies
 - Policy makers and authorities, international
 - Policy makers and authorities, national
 - Policy makers and authorities, regional or local
 - Citizens
 - Standardisation bodies
 - Innovators
 - End users (practitioners, farmers, etc.)
 - Education/training organisations/learners
 - Research infrastructures
 - Business accelerator providers
 - Other
 - Applicable to all

This phase is expected to be completed by month 12 (M12), and its output is expected to be included in the D5.2 Deliverable (M20). F6S will organise a two-hour online workshop with all

partners in M11-M14 to validate the final version of this output, which will be updated throughout phases 1 and 2. F6S will provide a template for the Exploitable Results to all partners as displayed in *Annex A/ Table 1A - Exploitable Results*.

The identification of KER started at the beginning of the project but will be iterated throughout CONCEPT. Table 4 shows the activities foreseen for Phase 1 and the proposed timeline for completion.

TABLE 4- PHASE 1 IDENTIFICATION ACTIVITIES

MONTH	ACTIVITY	DESCRIPTION
8	Exploitation Survey	Collecting individual inputs from each project partner
9	Data Processing and Analysis	Conducting a thorough examination of the gathered inputs
10	Concept Results Table	The table will include an overview of results, key exploitable results (KER), other exploitable outcomes, and individual partners' exploitation paths
11	Results Validation Workshop	A dedicated workshop to validate and refine the results
12	Definition Of Next Steps	Evaluating the outcomes and outlining the subsequent strategic actions

5.1.1.2 PHASE 2 - CHARACTERISE

In the second phase, the owners of each result will focus on characterising it as a preliminary step towards exploitation. This involves detailing the problem addressed by each result, identifying alternative solutions, and highlighting unique selling points. Additionally, the owners will assess competitors and the potential market to position their results effectively.

The output of this task will be a detailed table characterising each project result, encompassing the following information:

Problem: Describe the problem being addressed (i.e., the problem faced by potential users). Potential users include individuals, companies, organisations, etc., who are expected to use the result and generate impact. They are the "customers."

Alternative solutions: explain how "customers have traditionally solved the problem."

Unique selling point (USP) / unique value proposition (UVP): detail the competitive advantages and innovative aspects. Describe how your solution outperforms alternatives, its benefits to users/customers, and how it solves their problem more effectively than existing solutions. Highlight what distinguishes the key exploitable result (ker) from the competition.

Description: provide a concise description of your result and/or solution (e.g., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use straightforward language, avoid acronyms, and clearly explain how the UVP is delivered.

Market – target market: describe the market where your product/service will be utilised or can compete, addressing the following questions:

- What is the target market?
- Who are the customer segments?

Go-to-market – Competitors: identify your "competitors" (those offering alternative solutions). Compare their strengths and weaknesses to your solution.

F6S has prepared a template for characterising each result (ANNEX B). The primary owner identified in the output of phase one is responsible for leading the characterisation process for their exploitable result and completing the output table. F6s will moderate a one-hour workshop where the owners will validate the characterisation of each exploitable result.

5.1.1.3 PHASE 3 - OWN

The third phase focuses on specifying the intellectual property rights (IPR) and protection of each project result. Partners will identify their contributions to each result (foreground) and describe any pre-existing information or technology used (background). During this phase, partners will also define their individual interests in exploiting each result.

The output of this phase is a comprehensive results ownership list, which will include the following information:

- **Single or joint ownership of results:** number of owners
- **Result owners:** project partners
- **Will the owners exploit the results?:** yes / no
- **Availability:** in what form will the result be made available to other consortium members and/or third parties?
- **Access to background:** does the exploitation of the results require access to the background of one or several consortium members?
 - Identify the background
 - Measures taken/envisaged to provide access to the required background for exploitation
- **Access to third-party IPR:** does the exploitation of the results require access to third-party IPR?
 - Identify the background
 - Measures taken/envisaged to gain access to the required IPR

F6s will gather information from the partners to populate the table (included in Annex A) and organise one or two one-hour workshops to validate the outputs.

5.1.1.4 PHASE 4 - EXPLOIT

In this phase, partners will define the steps required for the exploitation of each project result. This includes establishing the use and business models, conducting a risk assessment, and creating a priority map. For each result, partners will develop an exploitation roadmap to plan activities post-project completion.

- **Actions:** Briefly describe the actions planned for execution 3-6 months after the project ends.
- **Roles:** Define the roles of partners involved in the above actions.
- **Milestones:** List the milestones and key performance indicators (KPIs) for monitoring the implementation of the actions, along with the timeline.
- **Financial Costs:** Estimate the costs for implementing the planned activities over 1 year and 3 years.
- **Revenues:** Project the revenues and potential profits from the key exploitable result (KER) 1 and 3 years after its use.
- **Other Sources of Coverage:** Identify resources needed to bridge the investment required to increase the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and ensure the result's use.
- **Impact in 3 Years:** Describe the impact in terms of growth and societal benefits over a 3-year period.

Additionally, partners will identify risks associated with exploitation, specify relevant mitigation measures, and create a priority map for these risks. This will be documented in two key outputs:

- **Risk Matrix:** This tool helps partners identify the types of risks, their importance relative to use, the probability of occurrence, and the probability of success of the mitigation measures.

- **Priority Map:** Provides a snapshot of the main identified risks.

The templates in Annex B document these activities. The outputs from phases 2 and 4 will be compiled into an Exploitation Roadmap for each exploitable result in the project (see Annex B). F6S will facilitate workshops for each exploitable result to validate the produced exploitation roadmap. For some key exploitable results, a second workshop may be held to delve deeper into the exploitation activities, with support from the Horizon Results Booster.

The Exploitation activities and Business Plan preparation, starting at month 6 and spanning to the end of the project, as defined in the GA, will be the responsibility of UIO and the SMEs. F6S will facilitate the exploitation activities to the completion of the exploitation plan herein defined. This includes market and competition analysis, SWOT and PESTLE analysis to define the external environment, financial analysis, the proposition of marketing activities and seeking additional funding opportunities.

F6S will regularly review and assess the 'Freedom to Operate' (FTO) in the areas of exploitable outputs. F6S will guide the partners for their FTO and patentability search, but each partner will be responsible for properly managing its results.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This document has been developed following the initial exploitation strategy outlined in the Grant Agreement. It reflects the ongoing discussions with partners to understand their vision and exploitation goals during the first six months of project execution. Serving as a guiding framework, the CONCEPT Exploitation Strategy Plan provides partners with insights into shaping a robust pathway for utilising CONCEPT results in their post-project journey. With three years and a half remaining in the project, it is essential to recognise that adaptations and modifications may be necessary. Therefore, this document is open to changes and is designed to respond to the evolving needs of the consortium in line with project objectives.

The communication and dissemination strategy detailed herein establishes a comprehensive approach that all consortium partners will follow throughout the program. This ensures that

communication efforts are aligned with defined guidelines and achieve the expected results. Our core objective is to develop alternatives to traditional silicon semiconductor technology by leveraging the expertise of leading European partners in chemistry, materials science, and device engineering. Through atomic layer deposition (ALD), we aim to integrate epitaxial functional complex oxides into neuromorphic and photonic devices at low temperatures, promoting sustainability and energy efficiency.

The communication strategy promotes the project and highlights its contributors. This document also defines the project's exploitation roadmap, methodology, and preliminary results, representing the strategy to achieve a definitive exploitation plan throughout the CONCEPT project lifecycle and beyond. This initial version of the exploitation plan will be updated in month 24 (D 5.2) and will lead to the final version in month 40 (D 5.4).

A structured communication strategy is essential for aligning project content with objectives and ensuring messages are transmitted clearly and engagingly. We have set short-term and long-term goals to generate awareness for developing alternatives to traditional silicon semiconductor technology and to share relevant project developments and outcomes. Our visual identity aims to make the project memorable and easily recognisable while presenting complex topics clearly and accessible.

This document also serves as a strategic guide for CONCEPT's exploitation activities, providing a tailored innovation management methodology to facilitate the development of a cohesive exploitation strategy post-project completion. The outlined exploitation activities will help partners understand the exploitation pathway for CONCEPT's results and the steps required to advance in research, technological, and commercial exploitation routes.

By fostering continuous feedback from users and ensuring the feasibility and long-term viability of the solutions, CONCEPT will utilise a customised methodology based on the Customer Discovery Loop. The methodology aims to achieve a validated business model, positioning partners with a clear go-to-market plan and increasing customer readiness levels throughout the project.

In the context of European-funded research projects, creating an effective exploitation plan is crucial for maximising the impact of developed technologies. By aligning project goals with

market needs and ensuring compliance with funding requirements, intellectual property management, and stakeholder collaboration, CONCEPT aims to deliver innovative solutions that generate significant economic and societal benefits.

7 ANNEXES

ANNEX A: EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

Table 1A - Exploitable Results.

This table will be further elaborated and validated in a workshop.

Name	Description	Type ¹	Owners/WP	KER ²	Target audience ³

¹ SCI — Scientific discovery, model, theory (...); PROD — Product (new or improved); SERV — Service (new or improved); PROC — Industrial process (new or improved); BUS — Business model (new or improved); DSG — Design (new or improved); METH — Method, material, technology, design (new or improved); PO — Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy; EVNT — Event (conference, seminar, workshop); STAFF — (qualified personnel exchanges); LEARN — learning and training (learning modules, curricula); INFRA — new or improved infrastructures or facilities

² High scientific potential; High societal potential (other than climate or environmental); High societal potential; High technologic, business or economic potential; High policy or regulatory potential; N/A

³ Researchers; Industry, business partners; Investors; EU Institutions and/or agencies; Policy makers and authorities, international; Policy makers and authorities, national; Policy makers and authorities, regional or local; Citizens; Standardisation bodies; Innovators; End users (practitioners, farmers, etc); Education/training organisation/ learners; Research Infrastructures; Business accelerator providers; Other; Applicable to all

Table 2A - Results Ownership List.

Single or joint ownership of results	Result owners	Will the owners exploit the results?	In which form will the result be made available to other consortium members and/or third parties?	Does the exploitation of the results require access to the background of one or several consortium members?	Does the exploitation of the results require access to third party IPR?
[number of owners]	Partners	(Yes / No)	[Sale of IP] [Licensing] [Open access] [Open source] [Free licence] [Secret/non-disclosure agreement] [Other] [N/A]	Identify the background Insert measures taken /envisaged to give access to the background required for exploitation	Identify the background Insert measures taken /envisaged to get access to the required IPR

ANNEX B: TEMPLATE FOR RESULT EXPLOITATION ROADMAP

Table 1B - Characterisation table.

KER NAME	
Problem	<p>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have).</p> <p>Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</p>
Alternative solution	Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition/current solutions?
Description	Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.

"Market" – Target market	Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?
Go to Market – Use model	Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, licence agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc.
Go to Market - Competitors	Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses compared to you?
Market maturity	State of the market targeted by this result: Not yet existing and not clear if market can be created; Market creating: not existing but potential for the creation of a new market; Emerging: growing demand, scarce supply; Mature: the market is already supplied with similar products.
Go to Market - Timing	What is the time to market?

Table 2B - Exploitation activities

Actions	Briefly describe actions planned to be executed 3-6 months after the end of the project.
----------------	--

Roles	Roles of partners involved in the actions defined above.
Milestones	List the milestones and KPIs to be used for monitoring the implementation of the actions listed above. Add timeline.
Financial Costs	Cost estimation to implement planned activities (1 year, 3 years).
Revenues	Projected revenues and eventual profits once the KER will be used (1 and 3 years after use).
Other sources of coverage	Resources needed to bridge the investment needed to increase TRL and ensure the result is used.
Impact in 3-year time	Describe impact in terms of growth/benefits for the society.

Table 3B - Risks assessment

Risk No.	
Degree of criticality of the risk related to the final achievement of this Key Exploitable Result Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low- 10 high).	
Probability of risk happening Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	
Risk Grade	

Potential intervention	
Estimated Feasibility/Success of Intervention Please rate from 1 to 10 (1 low - 10 high)	
Conclusion	

Priority map

